

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

AI, free will and autonomy - Introduction & Literature review

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Deliverable Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence in multiple aspects of our daily lives poses a great challenge in shaping civic participation within societies. Effective civic engagement finds its foundation in the empowerment of citizens who actively participate in public discourse, and in the articulation of their viewpoints. Understanding the dynamics that underpin trust in democratic institutions in this new context is thus important.

Module A questions individuals' capacity to navigate AI-based content and recommendations while safeguarding their autonomy and free will. Module B examines the requisites for the utilisation of AI to preserve institutional trust. Indeed, the use of AI in a wide range of fields could generate situations that are, or are perceived to be, unfair, thereby threatening the social balance established between members of the same community. Module C puts the new challenges posed by technological transformations into perspective, by analysing historical precedents and how they have shaped culture and social interactions over centuries.

Through a comprehensive exploration and assessment, modules A, B and C of KT4D's Social Risk Toolkit will seek to address an important challenge: identify exactly where regulation is needed to ensure that AI benefits society as a whole, and identify the conditions for trust in social institutions, in order to guarantee effective public debate and societal choices are made by citizens themselves.

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Introduction

The question underlying the action research carried out in this module is the following: How to act online in accordance with one's true interests? Will AI disrupt our ability to make good decisions for ourselves? In trying to answer these questions, we will explore the ways in which artificial intelligence can affect individuals' free will and autonomy.

According to *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*:

The term "free will" has emerged over the past two millennia as the canonical designator for a significant kind of control over one's actions [with] Questions concerning the nature and existence of this kind of control (e.g., does it require and do we have the freedom to do otherwise or the power of self-determination?), and what its true significance is (is it necessary for moral responsibility or human dignity?).¹

Free will is the ability of individuals to determine freely and on their own how to act and think. In the context of artificial intelligence, the philosophical question of free will arises as more and more choices, decisions, opinions, and attitudes seem to be constrained by the way the digital world is structured. In particular, the question of the information we process online is at the heart of the matter: how can we be free as individuals, and as members of a society, if **1) our own preferences are influenced by the way information is selected by algorithms** and **2) we only have low control over the choices we make online?**

The first part of module A therefore explores the central question of the relationship to information in a world where AI is used on a massive scale. In particular, we will look at the extent to which individual opinions are influenced by algorithms proposed by private parties, with their own motivations. To ensure that citizens' perspectives are truly incorporated in political decision-making, individuals must not only possess the capacity but also the motivation to cultivate well-informed opinions. The propensity to form opinions that accurately reflect reality, underpinned by evidence-based reasoning, is at the heart of effective collective decision-making processes.

The second part of this module will focus on the issue of individuals' ability to effectively make their own decisions and act independently, and to determine their own rules and objectives. In ethics and bioethics, patient autonomy is a key principle that emphasises a person's right to make decisions about their own medical treatment. Many of our online experiences suggest that individual autonomy cannot be taken for granted. New forms of subordination have emerged that do not arise from censorship or physical constraint, but from a voluntary submission to our immediate desires, and from the way the choices that we come to make online are presented to us. We are asked to accept terms and conditions, but to what extent do we truly accept these terms, if we are not in the position to do otherwise?

In what follows, we set out the main conclusions drawn from the literature in psychology on these issues. We also present a series of experimental protocols aimed at clarifying the boundaries of informed use of AI-based algorithms and systems.

¹ <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/freewill/>

State of the art: literature review

Social networks like Facebook and X (formerly Twitter) are often blamed for spreading 'fake news', manipulate people's opinions, and/or being used by foreign countries to destabilise democracy.² But what does it really imply? Are we as vulnerable to manipulation as this criticism suggests? What is our relationship with the online information we are exposed to?

In this literature review, we will consider **two questions**. The first concerns **the influence that online information has on us, and our ability to form personal opinions** without being influenced by algorithms. The second is about **the preservation of our autonomy when our attention is so easily captured by online systems designed for that purpose**.

AI-based information curation and its influence on people's opinions

There is a substantial literature on the psychology of belief, and important advances have been made in recent years on the impact of social networks and misinformation on citizens' opinions and attitudes.

AI-based algorithms have become very good at providing information that “suits” the user

The interplay between online information ecosystems and human cognitive processes has been extensively studied from a variety of perspectives. An important insight from neuroscience research is that not only are we wired to be attracted to relevant stimuli, but information itself activates the reward system (Kang et al., 2009; Ligneul et al., 2018). A piece of information is all the more attractive as it possesses some cognitive appeal – and information can be crafted for that purpose (Acerbi, 2019a).³ This involves elements of heightened social relevance and implications that enhance their cognitive attractiveness.

In the modern world, the variety of diverse foods has led to the widespread consumption of unhealthy diets, primarily due to the exploitation of human instincts, which historically associated taste with nutritional value. Similarly, AI-generated content may affect our information environment, making it more difficult to discern accurate information. Although the comparison to snack foods is limited, it remains useful to illustrate how changes in our environment can complicate our ability to understand reality.

Content-based appeal

Information can be attractive *per se* because it concerns aspects of reality that, if true, would have important implications for the self. If the information is plausible, and even if there is still a strong possibility that it is not true, its implications may be sufficiently interesting to be attended to.

² For instance, a global survey carried out by UNESCO and IPSOS in 2023 found that more than 85% of people were worried about the impact of online disinformation and 87% believed it had already harmed their country's politics.

https://www.unesco.org/sites/default/files/medias/fichiers/2023/11/unesco_ipsos_survey.pdf

³ False information can be manufactured based on features that make them attractive in an almost unconstrained way, whereas “true” news cannot, simply because they need to correspond to reality. False information can be intentionally crafted to propagate more extensively than accurate information.

Information is indeed more appealing to the human mind when it concerns central, relevant aspects of human life. This is the case for negative content (Bebbington et al., 2017), content related to threats (Blaine & Boyer, 2018), or disgusting content (Eriksson et al., 2016). The preference for negative stimuli – or negativity bias – has an evolutionary explanation, as individuals who better detect dangerous or negative elements of their environment are more likely to survive. Brain responses to sensory, cognitive, and motor stimuli are, in addition, more intense for negative stimuli (Ito et al., 1998).

Moreover, if such information is relevant to oneself, it is also relevant to others. It makes senders appear more competent than neutral or positive information (Boyer & Parren, 2015). On social media, alarmist headlines receive more attention than reassuring ones. In-lab experiments simulating real-world communication on social media confirm that, as information is passed from one individual to another, messages generally tend to become shorter and their content increasingly distorted, but risk-related information, on the contrary, are progressively exaggerated (Moussaïd, Brighton & Gaissmaier 2015).

Another feature that increases the attractiveness of information is **when it is both sufficiently surprising and sufficiently plausible to resonate optimally with one's prior knowledge.** This aspect is related to a stream of research in cognitive anthropology (Boyer, 2007; Boyer & Bergstrom, 2008) that has looked at supernatural concepts in religious beliefs and has demonstrated that a concept is more likely to achieve a cognitive optimum in terms of cultural transmission if it violates a few intuitions while being otherwise consistent with the individual's model of the world. In the case of fake news, the information is often very surprising, but plausible enough (at least to some part of the population) to be shared with some success, i.e. to be accepted by others as valuable information.

Finally, more attention is generally paid to socially related content such as gossip, i.e., information about intense third-party social relationships (Mesoudi et al., 2006). More generally, the literature on cultural evolution suggests that social information tends to attract more attention and be more easily remembered than non-social information.

Explanatory power

Information can also be attractive because it contributes to a powerful explanatory framework, which, if true, would make better sense of reality. Making sense of reality is useful in taking action, and in general, we like information that has explanatory implications on aspects of the world that escape us (Lantian et al., 2020). Problem-solving is associated with pleasure and "Aha!" moments (when we suddenly grasp the solution to a problem) promote the retention of memories. Similarly, superstition has been interpreted as an adaptive tendency to falsely detect the presence of a causal link, to avoid missing it when it turns out to be real (Beck & Forstmeier, 2007; Foster & Kokko, 2008; Shermer, 2022). It also predicts the perception of illusory control (Griffiths et al., 2019). Again, the bottom line is that the benefit of holding the information to be true outweighs the consequences of being wrong if it turns out to be false. A little bit of falsehood does not always make our models of the world unfit for our purposes (Cushman, 2020).

An intuitive way to explain why certain kinds of things happen is to see them as the result of intentional action. The literature on supernatural beliefs that we mentioned earlier emphasises that we are cognitively biased to detect intentionality wherever we look. This teleological bias makes us interpret information in a certain way (Wagner-Egger et al., 2018). Conspiracy theories exploit this tendency of

the human mind to gain traction and be massively shared. Van Prooijen et al. (2018) conducted a study on the link between teleological and conspiratorial thinking. They showed that participants who were most likely to perceive patterns in a series of random coin flips or abstract paintings (e.g. Pollock's work) were also those most likely to subscribe to conspiracy theories and to develop conspiratorial thinking. This tendency to illusory pattern perception also predicts people's receptivity to pseudo-profound bullshit, i.e. statements that appear to be very profound at first sight, but which are in fact meaningless (Walker et al., 2019).

It also appears that people are more likely to believe in conspiracy theories when they involve events that they feel the need to explain (Lantian et al., 2020). In addition, people are more attracted to conspiracy theories when important psychological needs are frustrated, for instance when feeling socially excluded (Graeupner & Coman 2017). Individuals with a strong need for uniqueness and for feeling special would also be more likely to value privileged access to secret information (Lantian et al., 2017), which is precisely what characterises conspiracy narratives. They foster a feeling of being able to understand the world in depth, to comprehend it from a global point of view rather than from a subjective and necessarily limited perspective. The need to feel unique would thus increase the tendency to believe in these theories. Besides, belief in fake news seems to be associated with various psychological dimensions such as delusion, dogmatism and religious fundamentalism (Bronstein et al., 2019).

Related to this need for explanation is the notion of **Need for Closure** (Kruglanski & Webster, 2018), which characterises an individual's tendency to consider an answer as definitive, i.e., to "seize and then freeze on early judgments". The scale developed by Roets & van Hiel (2007) includes items such as: "I don't like situations that are uncertain". This notion illustrates the importance for individuals to maintain a coherent knowledge system. This need for meaning can contribute to privileging straightforward information with strong explanatory power, at the expense of true information that is more complex and less relevant for the individual.

Reasons for emotional stances

Finally, **information can be attractive because it fosters the development of emotions and attitudes that we already hold**. In such cases, the truthfulness of the content may be less important than the emotion it induces, be it negative, such as anger or indignation, or positive, such as joy or pride. Whether the information is accurate does not really matter in such cases. Most important is the fact that the induced emotion can be justified and shared (Schaffner & Luks, 2018).

Baum, Frömer & Rahman (2020) specifically studied how emotions influence the perceived credibility of internet headlines featuring personalities unknown to participants. They show that emotionally-valenced titles elicited faster, more extreme, and more trusting judgments than neutral titles, including when they came from sources deemed to be unreliable. The measurement of pupil dilation (as a proxy for the attentive effort engaged) also varied with the emotional valence of the titles. This study confirms the central role of emotions in the way false information is evaluated on the internet.

Shallow vs. deep engagement with information

Information can be accepted while being only partially understood when it is being used not to derive consequences from its content but for other goals such as demonstrating affiliation or self-justification (Sperber, 2008).

From an individual's perspective, the utility of knowing the truthfulness of a particular fact is indeed limited and depends on the context. The importance of an accurate representation of reality depends on the intended use of the information – it may be crucial or just an added benefit. And **in many cases, shallow engagement with information is often sufficient**. Plausibility rather than certainty may be sufficient, depending on one's particular purpose, whether for oneself or in communicating with others. **In such a context, there is no longer a strong epistemic barrier to misinformation.**

Sharing is not believing

There is no need to assume that misinformation is knowingly shared as such. The premise that so many people believe things that are so obviously false is a bit too puzzling. Do they genuinely endorse this information? If they don't, it would no longer be necessary to resort to the idea that people are generally extremely gullible. But what is the point in sharing information if you don't believe it?

Sharing information, whether in real life or on social networks, does not always have the function of directing others' attention to the facts of the matter. It can also be used to emphasise the relevance of an idea, and to illustrate a certain epistemic position. It can also be an indirect way of expressing an opinion or manifesting an attitude or an emotion. While some online players do indeed aim for outright disinformation (Elsawah & Howard, 2020), most people who share information on the Internet do not do so with the malicious intention of misleading others. Indeed, **conveying genuine information is not always the primary goal of communication**, especially when it comes to communication on the internet (Acerbi, 2019b). Again, we care about truth to the extent that it is relevant to us and to those with whom we are sharing the information.

Of course, false information may slip through the cracks of our epistemic vigilance, and we may accept information that we would have rejected if we had been more careful or informed. We do not want to be misled by knowledge that could harm us, nor do we want to be caught spreading false information, as we care for our reputation. Generally speaking, however, our vigilance adapts to the level of accuracy that fits our purposes.

The pragmatic use of language is an essential aspect of human communication and has evolved alongside it. As content can be produced and shared at minimal cost, for example by sharing an article without reading it, the sharing of information can be interpreted in many ways: as a way of conveying or approving its content, as a way of highlighting its existence, as sarcastic, as an attempt to impress others about the breadth of our information and knowledge, etc. We use the Internet to exchange views, opinions and attitudes. It can be used to signal a political or social affiliation (Osmundsen et al., 2021) or to share something fun or interesting (Acerbi, 2019a). A study by Berriche & Altay (2020) shows, for example, that most of the posts that were published on a scientific misinformation website were phatic posts, meant to create social bonds, and not to provide informational content. There is, also, a well-established gap between what people read in private and what they share on social networks to demonstrate their expertise (Bright, 2016).

Thus, content shared on social media does not carry a strong presumption of truthfulness. Several results support this interpretation. First, it seems that **people are not interested in the truthfulness of what they share**. The limited effects of the debunking techniques can be interpreted as pointing to the general irrelevance of truthfulness in this type of situation: the fact that people are sensitive to fact-checking and remembering that a given information has been debunked does not prevent them

from sharing it. In addition, **people commonly share information without even reading it** (Gabiolkov et al., 2016).

Even more striking are situations in which people advance patently false claims. Schaffner & Luks (2018), for example, showed a panel of participants two photographs of the respective inaugurations of Presidents Obama and Trump. While they were, otherwise, perfectly capable of discerning differences in attendance, one in seven participants identified Trump's inauguration photo as having attracted the largest crowd, despite the evidence. How should this type of response, that is so obviously made in bad faith, be interpreted? Schaffner & Luks argue that expressing an opinion without sincerely believing it can be a way of showing support for a preferred political party or candidate. The respondents do know that this communicative behaviour will be interpreted as such (that is, not *literally*) by others, and they use it to impose their own political views, acting *as if* the information were true (Lynch, 2022).

On the whole, people are vigilant when it matters

Humans have developed special cognitive skills dedicated to monitoring information that comes from others (Sperber et al., 2010). The cultural intelligence hypothesis developed by Michael Tomasello and his colleagues (Herrmann et al., 2007) or Robin Dunbar's social brain hypothesis (Dunbar, 2009) suggest that the several intellectual faculties that are specific to humans compared to other closely related species can be explained by the need for people to collaborate within a group for their survival. This selective pressure would have favoured a set of socio-cognitive abilities during the evolution of the species conducive to optimal collaboration within social groups.

In particular, understanding the intentions of others is central to our ability to exchange information and to evolve socially within social groups. This ability to monitor in a fine-grained fashion when one should or shouldn't trust others develops very early in life. Developmental literature has shown how, even at a very young age, children do not regard all information as equally reliable and can distinguish between sources according to their skills and intentions (Clément, 2010; Harris, 2012). For example, by the age of two, children can tell whether a source is competent or not and whether she is acting in their best interests. By the age of three, they can discriminate between a well-informed and an ill-informed source on the topic at hand.

These different cues to a source's credibility can be classified into two broad categories: those that relate to the source's competence and knowledge (whether the source is in a position to know) and those that relate to the source's honesty (that is, their sincerity and willingness to say what they believe to be true). Generally speaking, the wide range of literature on credibility indicates that **a reliable source is a competent source whose intentions are aligned with our interests** (Pornpitakpan, 2004).

The match between the interests of the source and their audience is a fundamental aspect of epistemic trust. In some communicative situations, expectations about the honesty of the source will not focus on the literal truthfulness of their explicit assertion, but on the relevance of the implicit message. If what matters is the ability to defend one's own values, there is no need to scrutinise accuracy. People may thus accept doubtful information in one communicative context (e.g., when defending a political position) while later seeking true information in order to make an informed decision. Thus, **the reliability of a source in a given communicative context is assessed in light of one's own objectives**.

Sharing the same goals as the audience and making them explicit is therefore key in eliciting trust. We trust sources that we know will send us genuine information at a level that is adequate for what we want to use it for.

Does high personalisation make information more persuasive?

Algorithms are critical to the management of the vast amount of information available on social media platforms. When users access a social media news feed, they may be presented with hundreds or even thousands of stories from friends, followed pages, and sponsored content. Without some form of curation, identifying valuable information would be challenging.⁴ But the question is, how fine-tuned to people's previous behaviour should the selection be, while still preserving people's autonomy?

Personalisation can significantly enhance the persuasiveness of messages. By tailoring content to individual tastes and preferences, it is possible to create highly engaging experiences, whether for entertainment or information. AI can enable behavioural interventions to be more personalised and contextual for individual consumers by accounting for their unique traits and the specific environments they are in. Combining usage data (created when people use online services) with personal data (relating to an identifiable person), makes it possible to draw up extremely precise files on individuals, their tastes, their interests, and so on. They can be given a personalised pitch for a target message based on their existing views and personality: in theory, they could be given the arguments that are most persuasive to them, given their pre-existing beliefs. AI systems, particularly LLMs, thus have the potential to become extraordinarily persuasive. These systems could outperform human persuasion by producing highly engaging content.

Limits to AI persuasiveness

Having access to a custom-made series that perfectly aligns with one's interests can indeed be extremely satisfying, and this can lead to interventions that are more effective, and sometimes more equitable. However, **when multiple sources compete for attention using personalised content, it becomes difficult for any single viewpoint to dominate or stand out.**

People also consume content — whether it is news, fiction, or other types of media — not only for personal enjoyment, but also because they want to be able to talk to others about it. Much of the power of persuasive media lies in its ability to be shared and discussed within communities, thereby amplifying its impact. **If a given content is proposed to a single person because it is highly personalised, it may also fail to resonate broadly.** Lack of shared experience could then diminish its value and reduce the motivation to consume it in the first place. In fact, previous research has shown that much persuasion comes from people being convinced by the media or government, and then passing that knowledge or belief on to others (Aarøe, 2011).

Finally, the fact that AI can help find very strong arguments is not necessarily a problem in itself. **If AI systems could create highly engaging content, such increased engagement could also benefit fact-checked and reliable content,** making true information more appealing than fake news. Given that people are already more exposed to reliable news, increasing the engagement of true information could have a positive impact.

⁴ The diffusion of the printing press generated a comparable panic, with intellectuals worried the world would “fall into a state as barbarous as that of the centuries that followed the fall of the Roman Empire.” (Adrian Ballet, 1685).

But the real bottleneck to influence remains the amount of attention people are willing to pay. Individuals have limited attentional capacity, and simply cannot pay attention to every issue, which limits the potential impact of even the most persuasive content. The idea that AI could ever persuade people of anything is thus not very plausible. AI's persuasiveness is likely to peak at levels barely surpassing the most charismatic and persuasive humans. The main limiting factor is attention; complex arguments require time and sustained focus, which humans are generally unwilling to invest. Even if an AI could write an exceptionally persuasive book, it is unlikely to change many minds if only a few people read it. Moreover, as people become aware of the potential for AI to create persuasive content, they will also become more critical and less easily swayed.

What does work

Significant opinion changes occur through sustained exposure to arguments and evidence, often conveyed by trusted individuals. Historical shifts in public opinion on issues like gay marriage or trans rights have largely resulted from generational changes and persistent discussions within social networks (Kiley & Vaisey, 2020). Personal experiences and conversations with friends, family, and colleagues have a greater impact on changing opinions than impersonal media.

For instance, direct experiences, such as meeting someone from a marginalised group, can be more persuasive than any written argument. Discussions in a familiar environment, where there is trust, are more likely to lead to a change of opinion. While indirect influences, such as media consumption, play a role, meaningful and repeated discussions are crucial for large-scale opinion shifts.

Despite the potential of AI to enhance argumentation quality, the main challenge remains scaling meaningful discussions. Efforts like canvassing, where people engage in conversations about important issues – e.g., Kalla & Broockman (2020) – have shown some success in changing attitudes. However, replicating this on a large scale is difficult. **Effective persuasion requires trust, empathy, and meaningful exchanges, which are challenging to achieve through impersonal AI-generated content alone.**

Individuals' autonomy in their online choices

The feeling of losing control that many people complain about when navigating the internet and using social media can be explained at the cognitive level, and corresponds to a loss of a sense of agency – i.e., our capacity to act autonomously and make decisions, that is, to be an agent. The challenge therefore lies in restoring a sense of agency in our interactions with digital interfaces. Importantly, **attention is an essential component of this ability. Indeed, the sense of agency lies in the link between attention and the control of action** (Haggard, 2008). To fully appreciate the implications of true agentivity when it comes to online information, a preliminary look at the psychology of attention is therefore useful.

How attention works

A first consideration is the distinction between types of attention. William James (1890) originally used the concept of effort to differentiate between voluntary and involuntary attention. However, contemporary terminology more commonly distinguishes between endogenous attention, which is internally generated by an individual's will, and exogenous attention, which is triggered by external stimuli, such as a pop-up notification that suddenly captures one's focus.

The ability to focus our attention depends on a whole network of brain areas. This means that attentional failures are less due to faulty mechanisms filtering perceptual information than to a lack of stabilisation of the attentional system operated by executive control. This kind of failure can happen when we do not set ourselves a clear and well-motivated goal for the action we are about to carry out. Conversely, **the clearer we define our goal (and the stronger our motivation to achieve it), the easier it is to sustain our attention.** As shown by the work of Di Bello et al. (2022) executive control is achieved by connecting together the prefrontal and parietal cortex and by locking this network into priority processing of relevant information. Deliberation and decision-making directed towards clear, defined goals thus need to be facilitated.

Recent research in neuroscience has also contributed to unravelling the temporal dimension of attentional mechanisms, which can operate several times a second (Petitmengin & Lachaux, 2013). An example of such a mechanism is the pre-attentive filtering of information. The use of emotionally charged stimuli in advertisements or notifications increases the automatic power of attraction that they have on our attention. **The only way to deal with such captivating exogenous stimuli is to rely on automatisms that are even more powerful and deeply anchored through the building of habits.**

How do algorithms influence people's choices?

Social networks can be described as systems designed to capture users' attention, which is then sold to advertisers through increasingly personalised and manipulative targeting strategies. An emerging perspective on understanding how social networks and digital applications capture attention involves **comparing these strategies to those used by casinos, the tobacco industry, or the food industry with sugary products**, as discussed by Natasha Schüll (2012). These tactics draw directly from psychological research, including the principle of maintaining a certain degree of unpredictability in the delivery of rewards.⁵

The role of design, the issue of addiction, and dark pattern techniques

Research analysing platforms through the lens of addiction and compulsion raises broader questions about the role of interface design, commonly referred to as **choice architecture**. Choice architecture is defined as the external environment in which individuals make decisions. A foundational concept in this field is the notion of *affordance*, which was developed by the psychologist James Gibson in the 1970s. Affordances refer to the properties of objects that naturally suggest their intended use. This concept has been crucial in the design of digital interfaces, focusing on the importance of creating interactions that are intuitive and obvious.

The integration of users' cognitive characteristics in the design process later expanded on this idea. This ecological approach consists in developing solutions that facilitate easy recognition of the actions required, promoting ease of use, ergonomic interfaces, and user-centred design. The aim is to design systems that are self-evident and minimise the cognitive effort required from users. However, the same approach can also lead to manipulation. The lack of friction in users' interactions with the system enables them to perform tasks with minimal attention, potentially releasing extra cognitive resources. At the same time, the quasi-automatic nature of these interactions reduces voluntary control and diminishes awareness of one's actions. This may result in increased time spent on certain activities or

⁵ Zatorre & Salimpoor (2013) used brain imaging to study the effects of different types of music on brain activity. It appears that the brain activities linked to the sensation of pleasure are triggered not only by the familiarity and predictability of a piece of music, but also, to some extent, by surprise and variability.

engagement in non-reflective behaviours. Thus, **while affordances can simplify and streamline user interaction, they can also encourage actions that occur with limited awareness or intentionality.**

Some platforms even rely on manipulative techniques like **dark patterns**, which are interfaces deliberately designed to deceive or manipulate users (Fitton & Read, 2019) by preventing users from exercising their autonomy. Some media have for example adopted a "click-bait" model, offering headlines that optimise their appeal, regardless of the actual relevance of the content to the user (with headlines such as "9 Out Of 10 Americans Are Completely Wrong About This Mind-Blowing Fact"). Such titles exploit a basic emotional language and arouse curiosity but do not provide enough information without clicking on them. In fact, the stories do not need to be particularly attractive themselves, as long as users are tempted to click on the link.

Dark patterns are tested on thousands of subjects to determine which parameters are most effective. As Adam Alter (2017) says in his book *Irresistible: The rise of addictive technology and the business of keeping us hooked*, "In 2004 Facebook was fun, in 2016 it's addictive". The combination of infinite scrolling and personalised recommendations creates an immersive experience that is similar to a tunnel, inducing a state of absorption and heightened concentration. The intensified perception of control further contributes to the difficulty of disengagement, and exiting the application demands a substantial effort and considerable motivation. These effects are all the more pervasive as the user lacks visual cues: like in the experiment by Wansink, Painter & North (2005) where the use of self-refilling soup bowls altered the feeling of satiety, users of platforms such as TikTok or Instagram no longer feel the need to get out of the tunnel.

Some of the challenges of the digital environment include the erosion of autonomy due to manipulative choice architectures, distraction and cognitive overload (Kozyreva et al., 2020). With such precise information on our behaviour, preferences, and attitudes, recommendation systems can recommend the "right" product, the "right" article, the "right" video, at the "right" time, etc. Algorithms are very effective at selecting content that consumers will perceive as pleasurable and addictive. Analysis of browsing data enables content to be proposed that is close to what users like, but sufficiently different for it to be new. The monetisation of user attention duration on digital platforms incentivises the deliberate curation of content aimed at capturing and prolonging user engagement. As we saw in the previous section, this strategy often involves the presentation of emotionally evocative, sensational, or highly captivating content to retain user interest, as certain content resonates more deeply with the human experience due to its relevance to fundamental aspects of life.

Are social networks addictive?

From a scientific point of view, addiction typically includes a compulsive desire, difficulties in controlling its use and, sometimes, a physical withdrawal syndrome. In the case of social media use, there is no physiological habituation. Social media use falls outside the scope of the DSM-V's recognition of behavioural addictions, limited to video games and gambling (see Box 1 "Are social networks threatening to psychological health?"). While not classified as a distinct pathology, social networking exhibits nonetheless addictive characteristics by exploiting vulnerabilities in the brain's reward system, a fundamental component of motivation (Sherman et al., 2016). Posting photos that generate numerous likes will trigger the release of dopamine. The strength of this reward, akin to compulsive behaviours observed in animal experiments and analogous to slot machines, intensifies with greater variability and randomness in the reward pattern. Strategies used to foster addiction

encompass diverse techniques such as infinite scrolling, notifications, likes, targeted recommendations, etc. These strategies build on priority alerts for cognitive processing and encourage engagement at the expense of ongoing activities. In France, a report published a few years ago (Adès et al., 2019) suggested that **vulnerabilities should be distinguished according to age group and individual characteristics**, and emphasised the role of content as much as time spent on screens. Time spent in front of a screen alone is not necessarily a sign of an addictive process. Most of the time, digital activities tend to co-exist with other occupations, not replace them. In some cases, they even reinforce them. And the intensity of online exchanges is accompanied by greater face-to-face socialisation.

Are social networks threatening to psychological health?

While the mental health of young people is deteriorating worldwide, with increasing cases of depression, anxiety and mental disorders (Twenge et al., 2021), the PISA report notes that in almost all the countries studied, loneliness at school has increased. For many experts, social networks are to blame. Between 2009 and 2012, the main social media platforms have undergone radical change, taking on a more toxic dimension: Facebook introduced the 'Like' button, Twitter the 'Retweet' function, and news feeds became algorithmic, based on engagement. As a result, social networks have disrupted social interactions. In France, 1 child in 4 feels they spend too much time on their phone, according to a survey by the Heaven agency.⁶ Yet correlation is not causation, and many other potential factors are at play. Studies on the effects of time spent on social networks are many and contradictory. Some studies conclude that there is a clearly identified effect on mental health, others that there is a weak association, and others that there is no effect at all. A meta-analysis suggests that there is indeed a negative effect, but that it remains very weak (Masciantonio et al., 2023).

However, screen time may not be a good variable. Many factors are confounded in the same analysis, including factors with positive effects on well-being. For example, a Pew Research Center study conducted in 2022⁷ shows that half of American teenagers born between 1995 and 2012 feel more accepted online than offline. Does active involvement in online exchanges determine the positive effects of social media? Some studies show that the more involved users are in content production, and the more they interact with other users, the less negative the effect on their mental health. In 2016, a study conducted in Quebec by Morin-Major et al. (2016) showed that the more friends adolescents had on Facebook, the higher their basal levels of cortisol, a hormone produced during stressful experiences. Conversely, the more photos and stories they exchanged, the lower the cortisol level, because the interactions were of better quality. However, other studies such as Beyens et al. (2020) do not find the same results.

The difficulty researchers have in finding consistent results stems from the fact that, more often than not, social networks are not studied per se, but screen time in general, and the population in general. For example, a study conducted by Orben & Przybylski (2019) on hundreds of thousands of British and American teenagers' data revealed a low association between digital technology use and adolescent well-being. But when these same data were analysed by considering only data corresponding to the use of social networks by young adolescent girls, this association was multiplied by four. Adolescent girls (especially between the ages of 11 and 13) are in fact on the front line: one solid finding is that

⁶ <https://heaven.paris/files/BORNSOCIAL2023.pdf>

⁷ <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2022/11/16/connection-creativity-and-drama-teen-life-on-social-media-in-2022/>

exposure to idealised bodies has a negative impact on body image (Orben et al., 2024). Young girls who undergo social comparison on these platforms are at greater risk of developing psychological disorders (Kleemans et al., 2018). In conclusion, there are indeed links between social networks and mental health problems, but these depend very much on the individual and the context in which individuals are exposed, and on the characteristics of the platforms (for example, the positivity bias is stronger on Instagram, there are more messages associated with anger on X, there is only video content on TikTok, etc.). A better understanding of the combinations that turn out to be toxic, will enable regulation that is better adapted to the problems of the users themselves.

Box 1 – Are social networks threatening to psychological health?

What does autonomy and freedom mean in this context?

Daily interactions with minor decisions, such as sharing content without fully engaging with it, participating in unintended controversies, or mindlessly scrolling through media, cumulatively exhaust our cognitive resources. This depletion impairs our capacity to engage in more substantial, introspective decision-making concerning our personal desires and identity.

Ability to decide what you want vs. Ability to do what you want to do

The ability to determine what we want differs from the capacity to act in pursuit of our goals. Philosopher Martha Nussbaum (2002) identifies **two essential aspects of empowerment**: first, the ability to adopt the role of an agent and **make decisions aligned with one's goals and values**; and second, the ability to **exercise one's agency effectively**, which involves executing decisions and converting intentions into concrete actions.

Autonomy of the will, that is, individuals' ability to decide for themselves the rules of behaviour they adopt, is an ideal that can never be attained. It is intrinsically unachievable because, as human beings, we are subject to physiological constraints beyond our control. Freedom, understood as the autonomy of the will, is therefore not an achievement whose preservation can be demanded, but a desirable horizon. In the late 1970's, the Belmont report⁸ had two convictions: the idea that individuals should be considered as autonomous agents (introducing the notion of informed consent); and also, the idea that vulnerable people should be given assistance and protection. However, these two notions are contradictory, as on the one hand, the individual is considered to be autonomous, and on the other hand, the patient is considered to be in a state of vulnerability (due to age or a particular condition).

Conditions of freedom

Freedom of choice can be achieved by combining reflexivity about one's choices with the regulation of attention and emotions. This approach is based on a Spinozist definition of freedom. For Spinoza, freedom is based on adequate knowledge of the causes that determine what we do. By understanding the stimuli that can trigger our behavioural automatisms, we can devise strategies to avoid them. As we deliberate, we question whether this influence is consistent with the goals we have set for ourselves. Our actions become free because we have checked their consistency with our goals before we act. Whether or not the world is ultimately determined has no incidence on our responsibility as social beings.⁹

This involves, on the one hand, developing the kinds of automatisms and habits that make us act spontaneously in ways that are consistent with who we want to be and what we think is right, and, on the other hand, developing a disposition that activates a more reflexive relationship with ourselves in certain situations, making us more capable of inhibiting unwanted automatic tendencies.

Willpower alone cannot be the key to freedom because it is exercised through both conscious and automatic actions, the analysis of their consequences, and deliberation. Rather, freedom consists in working on the formation of our own personality until we can effectively consider our spontaneous reactions in a given context as our own. **Automatisms that have not been submitted to reflexivity on**

⁸ The Belmont Report is a foundational document in the field of research ethics, particularly in the context of research with human participants. It was published by the National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research in the United States in 1979.

⁹ <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/spinoza-psychological/>

the part of the user, and are not explicitly recognised as acceptable for the achievement of their goals, thus reduce our freedom.

How to empower internet users

Discussion of the ethics of AI within experts' committees¹⁰ is set in a context where machines will most probably become increasingly efficient. One objective is thus to ensure that human beings do not risk abdicating their autonomy in favour of machines, and rather to empower individuals through technology. That said, as we saw in this module, it is interesting to think about alternative concepts of autonomy in the context of artificial intelligence, i.e. as the voluntary submission of individuals to the rules that they decide to prescribe for themselves, in accordance with their personal values, preferences and commitment. In this context, it becomes more a question of helping internet users to remain in a position to freely decide what they see, what they accept, what they want, etc.

Kozyreva et al. (2020) show the challenges posed by digital interfaces to human cognition, which undermines the well-being of individuals and the functioning of democratic societies. The only framework that can restore users' freedom is one that grants them **the power to inhibit their own automatisms and switch to deliberative mode**.¹¹ Of course, not all the mechanisms of influence mentioned above necessarily alter people's autonomy. The judicious use of these same techniques can help us strengthen our power to act. Rather, it is about helping people to use these tools to achieve the goals they have set for themselves. Empowerment involves a better control of one's automatic behaviours, and more visibility on the intentions and mechanisms underlying the systems themselves. As people are naturally concerned about attempts to manipulate them (Sperber et al., 2010), if people know what to expect, they will naturally be more vigilant.

Promoting reflexivity and metacognition

Reflexivity, the ability to reflect on oneself, is an individual disposition. It also develops over the long term, through exchanges with others, the acquisition of knowledge, and the ability to stand back. Communities of experts, particularly scientific ones, are a good example.

Taking a step back and analysing one's own behaviour and thoughts is often necessary. This process is known as metacognition and involves asking questions such as *Are these automatisms right for me, and should I resist them?* Secondly, analysing the system we are interacting with is also important: questioning the designers' intentions, the interface's possibilities for action and configuration, etc. As many studies point out (Kozyreva et al., 2020), many features of social networks undermine the exercise of this reflexivity. Giving people more control is not enough if they are not prepared to exercise it. Traditional transparency measures, such as tools provided by platforms like Facebook's "Why am I seeing this?" features are inadequate as they offer only superficial information and rely on active user engagement to be effective. And widespread acceptance of cookies by the majority may be more a result of limited alternatives than a conscious choice. Rather than empowering individuals, terms and conditions often demand the assent of users without providing any space for deliberation. Intricate language and extended document lengths can also contribute to creating an environment that lacks transparency and leaves users ultimately uninformed. Quite often then, giving users more

¹⁰ E.g., the High Level Expert Group on AI (HLEG AI) set up by the European Commission, the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), and AI4People Institute.

¹¹ There are, however, contexts in which the user follows selected automatisms, which have been deliberately selected for their effectiveness in achieving a certain goal.

possibilities is in fact a strategy for exploiting their consent and disguising collective disempowerment. While ostensibly free to navigate the Internet according to personal preferences, online choices made by individuals often contradict the notion of a conscious and autonomous self. This is linked to the problem of alignment between the tool and the user: the goals of social networks and platforms (who want to make money and keep the latter's attention as much as possible) are not aligned with those of their users (who want to buy items or find information and maximise their well-being).

Training and education

Training and education are key to promoting reflexivity. Studies on "dark patterns" have shown that consumers, even when they are aware of their existence, are not sufficiently equipped to avoid their manipulative effects. Information can only be effective if the user is able to understand it. Making internet users more autonomous can be partly achieved by increasing information literacy and cognitive resistance to manipulation. A valuable strategy for promoting autonomy in the context of social media usage involves the implementation of feedback mechanisms, such as tracking app usage time, setting alerts, and managing notifications. Such control tools can effectively mitigate excessive engagement, and they can also be incorporated into educational curricula, ensuring that individuals, particularly the youth, are equipped with the knowledge to navigate social networks responsibly.

Digital literacy and civic online reasoning

Digital literacy encompasses the knowledge and skills that the public needs to evaluate the quality of information coming from the media and to distinguish informational content from other types of content – for example, advertisements, opinion content or false information. One aim of researchers is to develop, especially in schools, an information culture, by exploring the media system, the relationships between journalists and other players in society, the role of citizens etc. (Tully et al., 2020; Vraga et al., 2022; Vraga & Tully, 2019). There is a wide range of literature on different ways of making people less vulnerable to misinformation through preventive interventions. The effects of interventions based on the use of red flags for unverified or debunked information (Clayton et al., 2020), on crowd wisdom (Allen et al., 2021; Martel et al., 2024) or on attention-priming techniques (Pennycook et al., 2021), have recently been explored. Researchers' attention has turned in particular to the dissemination of false information on social networks, adapting interventions such as inoculation to these changing environments. Inoculation is a technique introduced by McGuire (Compton, 2024) and inspired by vaccination, which consists of presenting a poorly argued claim on a subject in order to disqualify any future better-defended argument (Lewandowsky & van der Linden, 2021). It even seems to work in modifying already entrenched opinions. Based on this theory Roozenbeek & Van der Linden (2019) developed a game on the topic of fake news. The aim was to make people immune to fake news by putting them in the shoes of a disinformation agent. Fake news seems somewhat less reliable to the participants after they have played the game on social networks. Another approach called civic online reasoning has proved to be effective in improving the ability of high school and university students to detect dubious information, particularly on social networks (Wineburg et al., 2021). This approach is based on learning professional fact-checking techniques and is meant to be effective even in cases where disinformation is difficult to detect at first sight. However, such a strategy may fall short in cases where the problem lies in a lower motivation to know the truth on a given issue.

Box 2 – Digital literacy and civic online reasoning

Simple rules for information literacy can help users navigate and make sense of their social media feeds and other online information sources (see Box 2 “Digital literacy and civic online reasoning”). An experiment carried out in France is particularly instructive.¹² It aimed to make a group of consumers aware of the effects of misleading or manipulative interfaces, and then to encourage the right reflexes.¹³ The reputation lever could also be used (somewhat along the lines of the European Nutri-score¹⁴) to encourage users to leave a service they no longer endorse, by presenting a clear indication of how an operator respects certain criteria for example, in terms of design.

Possible interventions in information architectures

Far from being the result of an individual and voluntary effort, **reflexivity also depends on external and environmental mechanisms**. This means adapting the digital space, its structure and the transparency of these mechanisms. Various interventions are possible:

- 🌀 Banning dark patterns
 - Some practices undermine users' autonomy by reducing their ability to make their own choices. Beyond personal data protection, sanctioning cognitive manipulation as such is now widely considered. This concerns techniques known as *bad nudge*, which encourage users to make decisions that run counter to their interests, or *bad sludge*, which prevent them from acting in their own interests by creating artificial difficulties that hinder their freedom of choice. But then comes the delicate question of what can be considered a manipulative or misleading interface (Mathur et al., 2021).¹⁵ Where does the difference lie between marketing and manipulation? The designer's job is precisely to guide the user towards uses or services that may suit them. The question is whether this manipulation is positive or negative, which is quite difficult because there are no objective indicators to assess it. To date, public authorities do not have sufficient knowledge to understand these mechanisms precisely and prove their effects.
- 🌀 Nudge techniques
 - Nudge techniques are behavioural interventions in choice architecture that influence behaviour in a predictable way and in the desired direction, for example via default settings. However, these techniques are criticised for raising ethical issues:
 - Nudges typically influence behaviour unconsciously and automatically, without any epistemic cues allowing the user to deliberate before making a decision
 - Assessing the good intentions of those who implement these nudges is difficult: how can one assess these intentions in the absence of any real evaluation of these public policies? (Chevallier & Perona, 2022). And what about the implementation of nudges by private entities such as the platforms themselves?

¹² https://www.modernisation.gouv.fr/files/2021-12/DGCCRF_%20rapport%20final_version%20finale_20.12.21_MC%20%28002%29.pdf

¹³ See also the work on psychological inoculation (Compton et al., 2021; Lewandowsky & van der Linden, 2021; Roozenbeek & van der Linden, 2019)

¹⁴ https://nutriscore-europe.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/NS_rapport-EU-V10_230202.pdf

¹⁵ Article 25 of the DSA on the definition of manipulated interfaces.

Boost techniques

- Boost techniques are interventions designed to enhance users' cognitive and motivational skills, while preserving their decision-making autonomy. Typically, they can involve adding cues to the epistemic quality of information, or training people in simple rules of online reasoning. Different types of interventions have been explored to foster better online decision-making and resist manipulation. In one approach, individuals are inoculated against manipulation by enhancing their competence to detect such ads and make informed decisions. For instance, Lorenz-Spreen et al. (2021) showed that a short, simple intervention—prompting participants to reflect on their own personality—can significantly increase people's ability to accurately identify ads that were targeted at them. Personal reflection and feedback significantly improved the ability to correctly identify targeted ads.

Cognitive science-inspired technological interventions in information architectures could, for example, involve the introduction of frictions (e.g., when accessing offensive content). A paradigm shift towards a techno-cognitive approach that fosters users' reflexive and deliberative abilities should be encouraged, giving preference to the "boost" principle over the "nudge" principle (Chammat & Giraud, 2019).

Need of a less polarising environment

Empowerment is also about how individuals react to the information content they encounter. In most situations in our everyday lives, powerful motivational factors shape our relationship to information and direct the way we mobilise our reasoning skills. **For reasoning efforts to be aimed at truth, the argumentative context must be collaborative**, and individuals must be willing to detach themselves from their own perspective. The context in which communication takes place may in turn make the respective stakes of knowing the truth and maintaining useful beliefs more or less salient. This contextual component is perhaps the most important factor in tackling the challenge of false information on the Internet. A central aspect of citizenship is the possibility of authentic dialogue. In the current political climate, citizens as well as politicians seem to have an increasingly difficult time talking with those holding different opinions about important policy issues (Hess & McAvoy, 2014). **For many reasons, a great deal of dialogues we engage in lack the quality of dialogism and are, instead, monological.** This means that they end up reinforcing pre-existing views and, oftentimes, strengthening dominant or hegemonic voices. Respect and trust (about others' non-harmful intentions) are also essential features of authentic dialogue – and more generally of democratic settings (Boghossian & Lindsay, 2019) – and they imply listening to others. Reinforcing the ability of individuals to exchange information with others in a respectful way is probably one of the most interesting ways of making them more impervious to manipulation, and less tempted by the superficial use of fallacious arguments.

In any case, regulation is needed with a more collaborative and emancipatory vision, that would promote transparency in the intentions of online platforms and services – and not just in terms of getting users to sign agreements. To restore some control over automatisms, visibility of one's actions is a basic prerequisite. The burden of transparency and visibility must rest on the systems themselves, not on individuals. Regulations should take into account the psychological constraints of individuals by, e.g., questioning the genuine agreement of users with the terms and conditions in GDPR online

forms. This approach would align regulations with users' cognitive and emotional considerations, enhancing the transparency and ethical implications of algorithmic choices in digital environments.

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